

Weed control with a 2 μm laser beam: The effects on some annual and perennial weeds

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ABSTRACT: Several research and commercial projects are underway to develop autonomous vehicles equipped with lasers to control weeds in field crops. Recognition systems based on artificial intelligence have been developed to locate and identify small weed seedlings, and mirrors can direct a laser beam towards the target to kill the weed with heat. Laser weeding seems to be a promising tool to replace or supplement herbicides and mechanical control, with only a small treatment area in contrast to other weed control measures. Unlike herbicide spraying, laser weeding leaves no chemicals in the field that may harm non-target organisms after the treatment. Compared to mechanical weeding, laser weeding does not move the soil stimulating a new cohort of weeds to germinate. However, laser weeding is energy demanding; therefore, it is important only to use an energy dose that is sufficient to kill the target. A 2 μm laser beam was used to control weeds. We present dose-response experiments showing the effect of different energy dosages (Joule) on several weed species. We exposed the weed species to various laser dosages at the cotyledon, two-, and four permanent leaf stages. Some grass weeds were also irradiated. The species reacted differently to the laser dosages. Some species were very susceptible to the laser while others were less, especially at the largest developmental stage, where regrowth sometimes were observed.

Keyword: integrated weed management, dose-response, laser weeding, site-specific weed management, thermal weed control.